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Convective currents between open water and vegetation due to solar radiation

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Overview of Presentation

1. Introduction
2. Model Description
3. Governing Equations
4. Numerical Procedure
5. Analysis of the Results
6. Conclusions

Introduction

Convective Currents:

- thermally-driven exchange flow due to temperature difference
- are observed a) between shallow and deep water
b) between open water and aquatic vegetation
- vegetation prevents solar radiation from entering into the water body
- open water → higher temperature

Convective currents between open water and vegetation due to solar radiation

5th IAHR Europe Congress, Trento, Italy

Introduction

Aquatic Vegetation:

- present in shallow aquatic systems
- energy dissipation – additional drag
- reduces the current velocity
- common vegetation porosity $\phi = 0.70 - 0.97$

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Introduction

Effect of solar radiation

- additional source term in energy equation
- a) solar model based on Beer's Law
- b) solar model based on Radiative Transfer Equation (RTE)

Effect of Vegetation

macroscopic approach

- volume averaged theory
- additional resistance terms in momentum equations
- a) canopy flow theory
- b) porous media flow theory

Introduction

Objectives of the Study:

- Investigate
 - effect of differential water heating
 - characteristics of convective currents
 - effect of vegetation porosity on convective currents
- Compare numerical results with experimental data
 - For $\varphi=0.75-0.97$ [Zhang & Nepf, 2009]
 - For $\varphi=1$ [Coates & Patterson, 1993]

Model Description

- 2D model in a tank separated into 2 regions (open and vegetated)
- Open water is heated with constant surface radiation intensity
 $I_0 = 157 \text{ W/m}^2$
- Vegetation { consists of cylinders ($d = 6\text{mm}$)
 $\phi = 0.97, 0.85, 0.75$

Governing Equations

➤ **CFD commercial code:** Fluent 15.0.7

➤ **Unsteady Navier – Stokes equations**

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho U_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0$$

extra source term
due to vegetation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho U_i) + U_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}(\rho U_i) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right] + \rho \beta (T - T_0) g_i + F$$

➤ **Energy equation (Boussinesq approximation)**

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho c_p T) + U_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}(\rho c_p T) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\kappa \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right) \right] + S_h$$

extra source term
due to radiation
absorption

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Governing Equations

Internal drag resistance term F (vegetation)

Open Area: $F = 0$

Vegetated area:
$$F = -\phi \frac{v}{k} \rho \langle U_i \rangle - \phi^2 \frac{C_f}{\sqrt{k}} \rho \langle U_i \rangle |\langle U_i \rangle|$$

ϕ = vegetation porosity

k = intrinsic permeability

C_f = dimensionless parameter

ϕ	$k * 10^{-6}$	C_f
0.97	73.13	0.0323
0.85	5.04	0.0484
0.75	1.56	0.0510

Governing Equations

Radiative Transfer Equation (RTE)

$$\underbrace{\frac{dI(\vec{r}, \vec{s})}{ds}}_{\nabla \cdot (\vec{s}I)} + \underbrace{(a + \sigma_s)I(\vec{r}, \vec{s})}_{\text{absorbed and scattered radiation from the control volume}} = \underbrace{an^2 \frac{\sigma^{(s)} T^4}{\pi}}_{\text{emitted thermal background radiation. } n\text{-is refractive index, relative speed of light in vacuum and in medium}} + \underbrace{\frac{\sigma_s}{4\pi} \int_0^{4\pi} I(\vec{r}, \vec{s}') \Phi(\vec{s}, \vec{s}') d\Omega'}_{\text{scattered radiation from environment } \Phi \text{ is phase function, describing distribution of scattering directions}}$$

- σ_s : scattering coefficient
- \vec{s}' : scattering direction vector
- Ω : solid angle
- Φ : phase function

scattering is ignored, as the experimental studies on scattering of radiation in pure water, indicate that the scattering phase function Φ is highly forward in nature

Governing Equations

Internal heating source S_h (radiation absorption)

Vegetated area: $S_h = 0$

Open area: S_h according to Beer's Law:
$$S_h = \frac{1}{\rho \cdot C_p} \sum_{i=1}^N n_i I_i e^{-n_i(h-y)}$$

Simpler RTE form when scattering is neglected (S_h):

$$S_h = \frac{1}{\rho_o C_p} \sum_{i=1}^N (4 \cdot n_i \cdot \sigma \cdot T^4 - n_i \cdot G_i)$$

η_i = extinction coefficient

σ = Stefan-Boltzmann constant

G_i = incident radiation (total sum of absorption, emission and scattering on each cell)

$$\eta_i \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 145 \text{ m}^{-1} \\ 15 \text{ m}^{-1} \\ 2.5 \text{ m}^{-1} \end{array} \right.$$

Numerical Procedure

Boundary conditions:

- adiabatic no-slip wall boundary conditions
- left and right tank walls steady temperature T_o

Analysis of the Results

1. Uniform heating, $\phi=1$, Solar Radiation Model testing

➤ both solar radiation models are in a very good agreement with observed experimental data.

➤ marginal difference close to the heated surface due to emission term in RTE equation.

Analysis of the Results

2. Effect of grid size tested, $\phi = 0.97$

➤ no significant difference (<1%).

➤ grid size used 180,000 cells.

Analysis of the Results

Case studies

Case	ϕ	I_o (W/m ²)	h (m)	k (m ²) x 10 ⁻⁶	C_f
1*	1.0	127.5	0.3	-	-
2	0.97	157.0	0.1	73.13	0.0323
3	0.85	157.0	0.1	5.04	0.0484
4	0.75	157.0	0.1	1.56	0.0510
5	0.97	157.0	0.15	73.13	0.0323
6	0.85	157.0	0.15	5.04	0.0484
7	0.75	157.0	0.15	1.56	0.0510

- Comparison with experimental data [Coates & Patterson, 1993] *
- Comparison with experimental data [Zhang & Nepf, 2009]

Analysis of the Results

3. Differential Heating, $\phi = 1$, Temperature increase (dimensionless form)

➤ both models reproduce the observed data.

➤ the sharp increase is due to side wall effect.

➤ RTE model has slower temperature increase.

Analysis of the Results

4. Differential Heating, $\phi = 0.97$, Temperature Increase in dimensionless form

- temperature difference increases when the current reaches this location
- the slope of the numerical results in agreement with experimental data
- but in experiments there is heat loss (negative δT)
- the vertical solid line corresponds to wall impact.

Analysis of the Results

5. Porosity Effect on Temperature Increase

➤ both models present the same behaviour

➤ as ϕ decreases the temperature increase starts later in time.

➤ as ϕ decreases the temperature increase gets higher values for Beer's law model.

Analysis of the Results

6. Horizontal velocity (a) and temperature (b) contours for $\phi = 0.85$ and Beer's law model ($t = 100$ s and 500 s)

Analysis of the Results

7. Porosity effect on horizontal velocity contours (t = 450 s) with Beer's law model

Analysis of the Results

8. Porosity effect on Temperature contours (t = 450 s) with Beer's law model

Analysis of the Results

9. Horizontal velocity for $\phi = 0.97$ at $x = -0.09$ m

➤ both models reproduce the observed data

➤ depth increase shows a greater increase on velocity profile based on Beer's law rather than RTE.

Analysis of the Results

10. Porosity effect on horizontal velocity ($t = 500$ s)

➤ both models have same behavior

➤ RTE generates shallower current than Beer's law model.

Analysis of the Results

11. Variation of mean horizontal velocity at the light/dark boundary for all vegetated cases

➤ Velocity increases at the beginning the flow and is inertia dominated

➤ After a specific time the velocity remains constant and the flow is drag dominated

Conclusions

- The velocity of both the warm and the cold current is decreased with decreasing porosity.
- Both radiation models reproduce the observed data. The RTE model has a smoother temperature and velocity development due to the emission term in the equation.
- RTE simulates field conditions better, because it engulfs emission, absorption and scattering terms. It is CPU sensitive.
- Initially, the currents are inertia dominated and their velocity increases linear with time, while after a specific time instant they become drag dominated and their velocity remains almost constant.

Thank you for your attention...